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WINKNN: Windowed Intervals' Number kNN Classifier for Efficient Time-Series Applications

Chris Lytridis ¹

¹ HUMAIN-Lab, International Hellenic University (IHU), 65404 Kavala, Greece; lytridic@teiemt.gr (C.L.); chrhazi@teiemt.gr (C.B.); m.manios@teiemt.gr (M.M.)

² Institute of Robotics, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria; a.lekova@ir.bas.bg

* Correspondence: vgkabs@teiemt.gr; Tel.: +30-2510-462-320

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Abstract: Our interest is in time series classification regarding cyber–physical systems (CPSs) with emphasis in human-robot interaction. We propose an extension of the k nearest neighbor (kNN) classifier to time-series classification using intervals' numbers (INs). More specifically, we partition a time-series into windows of equal length and from each window data we induce a distribution which is represented by an IN. This preserves the time dimension in the representation. All-order data statistics, represented by an IN, are employed implicitly as features; moreover, parametric non-linearities are introduced in order to tune the geometrical relationship (i.e., the distance) between signals and consequently tune classification performance. In conclusion, we introduce the windowed IN kNN (WINKNN) classifier whose application is demonstrated comparatively in two benchmark datasets regarding, first, electroencephalography (EEG) signals and, second, audio signals. The results by WINKNN are superior in both problems; in addition, no *ad-hoc* data preprocessing is required. Potential future work is discussed.

Keywords: audio signal; big data; cyber–physical system (CPS); electroencephalography (EEG) signal; human-robot interaction (HRI); Intervals' Number (IN); kNN classification; time-series

1. Introduction

A cyber–physical system (CPS) has been defined as a device with sensing as well as reasoning capacities [1,2]. Strategic initiatives regarding CPSs include “Industrie 4.0” in Germany, the “Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT)” in the United States, and “Society 5.0” in Japan [3]. CPSs typically focus on multidisciplinary applications in healthcare, agriculture, and food supply, manufacturing, energy and critical infrastructures, transportation, logistics, security, and, lately, education [4]. Our interest here is in CPSs regarding human-robot interaction.

There is a need for supporting CPSs with mathematical models that involve both sensory data and structured software data toward improving CPS performance during their interaction with humans. However, a widely acceptable mathematical modelling framework is currently missing. In response, the lattice computing (LC) paradigm has been introduced [1,5] for hybrid mathematical modelling based on mathematical lattice theory that unifies rigorously numerical data and non-numerical data; the latter may include (lattice ordered) logic values, sets, symbols, and trees/graphs. More specifically, the cyber and physical components of a CPS are modelled involving non-numerical and numerical data, respectively, in any combination. An additional advantage of lattice computing is its capacity to calculate with semantics represented by a lattice (partial) order relation.

Human-robot interaction is, typically, driven by behavioral patterns including auditory and/or visual signals. Visual stimuli are very common in human-robot interaction applications, and are often

treated as time-series data. For example, in [6] recognition of time-series segments is used to treat hand gestures as natural language processing; furthermore, in [7] time series data are used for nod detection. Recent work has considered electroencephalography (EEG) signals toward improving decision-making, and the results have been encouraging [8–10]. Another important modality in human-robot interaction is speech [11]. More specifically, humans use a number of linguistic social cues (i.e., words or phrases that reveal sympathy, empathy, encouragement etc.) which could be especially useful toward an effective human-robot interaction.

Automated emotion recognition is important in human-robot interaction, for instance regarding the design of smart collaborative or assistive robots. Current aspects and future directions in emotion recognition using machine learning is shown in [12,13], where different machine learning techniques are proposed for recognizing emotions from physiological signals (EEG in particular). Note that data preprocessing and feature selections both are critical as well as computationally expensive. Table 3 in [12] presents some of the most popular features extracted from time-series including temporal, statistical, spectral, linear, and/or non-linear features. Classifiers used to recognize emotional states, typically, regard supervised learning including k nearest neighbor (kNN) [14–17], support vector machine (SVM) [17–19], Naive–Bayes (NB) [17], quadratic discriminant analysis (QDA) [20], artificial neural networks [21,22]. Furthermore, unsupervised and semi-supervised learning algorithms are also used [12].

Summarizing the bibliography research, both ad hoc feature extraction and classification of big data impose large feature dimensions resulting in high computational costs for training. To counter the aforementioned problems we propose using intervals' numbers (INs) in the framework of lattice computing (LC). Recall that LC has been defined as “an evolving collection of tools and methodologies that process lattice ordered data including logic values, numbers, sets, symbols, graphs, etc.,” [23,24]. We point out that LC is not merely an algorithm but rather it is an information processing paradigm. LC models are expected to be useful in CPS applications including human-robot interaction because they can (1) deal with both numerical data (regarding physical system components) as well as with non-numerical data (regarding cyber system components), (2) compute with semantics, represented by a partial-order relation, (3) rigorously deal with ambiguity represented by information granules, (4) naturally engage logic and reasoning, and (5) process data fast. LC suggests useful instruments for analysis and design of new technologies including formal concepts [25,26], type-2 fuzzy sets [23,27], and other. In the context of the LC framework, intervals' numbers, or INs for short, have been studied as explained next.

An IN is a mathematical object that can represent either a fuzzy interval or a distribution of samples [2,28–30]. Applications of INs have been reported to neural networks (NNs) as well as to fuzzy inference systems (FIS) [23,31–35]. INs are engaged here for massive data representation in time-series as explained in the following.

An advantage of an IN is its capacity to represent data statistics of all-orders using few numbers; more specifically, L numbers are used to define L intervals; hence, a significant data reduction may result in a capacity to process big data fast. Furthermore, no feature extraction is necessary since the all-order statistics, represented by an IN, are implicitly employed as features. An IN-based k nearest neighbor (kNN) scheme was introduced for classification by fuzzy lattice reasoning (FLR) in [5]. However, a drawback of the latter work, regarding classification of time-series using INs, has been the suppression of the “time dimension” because of the representation of a whole time-series by a single IN. A novelty of this work is a recovery of the “time dimension” by the windowed IN-based k nearest neighbor classifier, or WINkNN for short, which is applied comparatively on two different datasets, namely (a) a human brain EEG dataset for emotion recognition, and (b) an audio dataset for word classification.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 summarizes the useful mathematical instruments. Section 3 presents the methods as well as the datasets used in our experiments. Section 4

presents experiments and results as well as a discussion. Finally, Section 5 concludes by summarizing the contribution of this work; potential future work is also delineated.

2. Mathematical Background

This section summarizes instrumental mathematical results published elsewhere [23,30,31,34,36].

Given a lattice (L, \sqsubseteq) , a *valuation* is defined as a real function $v: L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that satisfies $v(x \sqcap y) + v(x \sqcup y) = v(x) + v(y)$, $x, y \in L$. A valuation is called *monotone* if $x \leq y \Rightarrow v(x) \leq v(y)$, and *positive* if $x < y \Rightarrow v(x) < v(y)$. A positive valuation function $v: L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ in (L, \sqsubseteq) defines a metric distance function $d: L \times L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$ given by $d(x, y) = v(x \sqcup y) - v(x \sqcap y)$. Extensions to Cartesian products follow.

A lattice (L, \sqsubseteq) may be the Cartesian product of N *constituent* lattices (L_i, \sqsubseteq) , $i = 1, \dots, N$, i.e., $(L, \sqsubseteq) = (L_1, \sqsubseteq) \times \dots \times (L_N, \sqsubseteq)$, where $(x_1, \dots, x_N) = \mathbf{x} \sqsubseteq \mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_N) \Leftrightarrow x_1 \sqsubseteq y_1, \dots, x_N \sqsubseteq y_N$. Positive valuation functions $v_i: L_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ in the constituent lattices (L_i, \sqsubseteq) , $i = 1, \dots, N$, respectively, define a parametric Minkowski metric function $d(\cdot; \mathbf{p}): L \times L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$ in the product lattice $(L, \sqsubseteq) = (L_1, \sqsubseteq) \times \dots \times (L_N, \sqsubseteq)$ given by

$$d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}; \mathbf{p}) = \left[(d_1(x_1, y_1))^p + \dots + (d_N(x_N, y_N))^p \right]^{1/p}, \text{ with parameter } \mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R} \quad (1)$$

where $x_i, y_i \in L_i$, $i = 1, \dots, N$, $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_N)$, $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_N)$. Next, we consider metrics in a lattice hierarchy.

A hierarchy of lattices in three levels is presented next, resulting in the lattice of *Intervals' Numbers* [34,36,37]. For each level, metric distance functions are introduced.

Level-0; The Lattice (\mathbb{R}, \leq) of Real Numbers: Assume the lattice (\mathbb{R}, \leq) of real numbers. The greatest lower bound of two numbers x and y is the smallest of the two, denoted by $x \wedge y$, whereas the least upper bound of two numbers is the greatest of the two, denoted by $x \vee y$. Positive valuation function $v: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ in lattice (\mathbb{R}, \leq) is any strictly increasing function. For instance, choosing $v(x) = x$ it follows that the distance between two real numbers x and y equals $d(x, y) = v(x \vee y) - v(x \wedge y) = x \vee y - x \wedge y = |x - y|$. Extending to the N -dimensional Euclidean space $(\mathbb{R}^N, \sqsubseteq)$, with $v(x) = x$ in every dimension, from Equation (1) there follows the Minkowski metric $d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}; \mathbf{p}) = \left[(d_1(x_1, y_1))^p + \dots + (d_N(x_N, y_N))^p \right]^{1/p}$ known in the literature as L_p *metric*. In particular, the L_1 metric $d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}; 1) = |x_1 - y_1| + \dots + |x_N - y_N|$ is known as *Hamming distance*; the L_2 metric $d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}; 2) = \sqrt{(d_1(x_1, y_1))^2 + \dots + (d_N(x_N, y_N))^2}$ is known as *Euclidean distance*; furthermore; the L_∞ metric equals $d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}; \infty) = \max\{|x_1 - y_1|, \dots, |x_N - y_N|\}$.

Level-1; The Lattice (I_1, \leq) of Intervals: In the lattice (\mathbb{R}, \leq) of real numbers, any strictly decreasing function is a *dual isomorphic* function. Consider the partially ordered lattice (I_1, \sqsubseteq) of intervals in the lattice (\mathbb{R}, \leq) . The greatest lower bound of two intervals $[a, b]$ and $[c, e]$ is given by $[a, b] \sqcap [c, e] = [a \vee c, b \wedge e]$ if $a \vee c \leq b \wedge e$, and $[a, b] \sqcap [c, e] = \emptyset = [+ \infty, - \infty]$ if $a \vee c > b \wedge e$; whereas, the corresponding least upper bound is given by $[a, b] \sqcup [c, e] = [a \wedge c, b \vee e]$.

Given (a) a positive valuation function $v: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, and (b) a dual isomorphic function $\theta: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ in (\mathbb{R}, \leq) , a positive valuation $v_1: \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ in the corresponding lattice $(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \geq \times \leq)$ of *generalized intervals* is defined by $v_1([a, b]) = v(\theta(a)) + v(b)$. Therefore, a metric distance in $(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \geq \times \leq)$ is given by:

$$d_1([a, b], [c, e]) = v_1([a, b] \sqcup [c, e]) - v_1([a, b] \sqcap [c, e]) = v(\theta(a) \vee \theta(c)) - v(\theta(a) \wedge \theta(c)) + v(b \vee e) - v(b \wedge e) \quad (2)$$

In conclusion, the metric $d_1(\cdot, \cdot)$, given by Equation (2), is valid in sublattice (I_1, \sqsubseteq) , which is embedded to the superlattice $(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \geq \times \leq)$.

Level-2; The Lattice (F_1, \leq) of Intervals' Number (INs): A *Generalized Intervals' Number*, or GIN for short, is defined as a function $f: [0, 1] \rightarrow (\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \geq \times \leq)$ where $(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \geq \times \leq)$ is a lattice of *Generalized Intervals*. Let G be the set of GINs; then, the (G, \sqsubseteq) is a lattice, as a (non-numerable) Cartesian product of complete lattices $(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \geq \times \leq)$. Next, the interest focuses on the sublattice of INs.

An intervals' number, or IN for short, is defined as a function $F: [0, 1] \rightarrow I_1$ that satisfies:

$$h_1 \leq h_2 \Rightarrow F_{h_1} \sqsupseteq F_{h_2}, \text{ and}$$

$$\forall X \subseteq [0, 1] : \bigcap_{h \in X} F_h = F_{\vee X}$$

The set F_1 of INs is a partially ordered lattice denoted as (F_1, \leq) . An IN is interpreted as a *grain* of information [36]. In particular, it has been shown that (F_1, \leq) is a metric lattice [38] whose metric function $D_1 : F_1 \times F_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$ is given by

$$D_1(F, G) = \int_0^1 d_1(F_h, G_h) dh \tag{3}$$

where the integrable function $d_1 : I_1 \times I_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$ is defined by Equation (2). For $L = F_1^N$ there follows a Minkowski metric given by Equation (1).

Parametric functions $v(\cdot)$ and $\theta(\cdot)$ may introduce tunable non-linearities whose parameters can be estimated optimally. In this work, toward reducing complexity during optimization, we consider functions $v(\cdot)$ and $\theta(\cdot)$ with only two parameters per function; in particular, we consider exclusively linear parametric functions $v(\cdot)$ and $\theta(\cdot)$:

$$v(x) = v_1x + v_0, \tag{4}$$

$$\theta(x) = \theta_1x + \theta_0, \tag{5}$$

3. Methods and Datasets

This section deals with data representation issues as well as the windowed IN kNN, or WINkNN for short, classifier. It also presents the datasets to be employed in the next section.

3.1. Intervals' Numbers (INs) and Time-Series Representation Based on INs

Probability and possibility distributions have been studied comparatively in the literature [39,40]. Furthermore, a possibilistic interpretation has been proposed for an IN [38] followed by a probabilistic interpretation [37]. In conclusion, an IN was established as a mathematical object, which can be interpreted either probabilistically or possibilistically [30].

Recall that an IN can be represented either as a function $F(x) = \bigvee_{h \in [0,1]} \{h : x \in F_h\}$, namely *membership-function-representation* or, equivalently, as set of intervals $F_h, h \in [0, 1]$, namely *interval-representation*. We point out the potential of an IN to represent time-series big data. More specifically, the big data here regards the (time-series) samples. For instance, consider the EEG time-series signal shown in Figure 1a. Figure 1b shows the corresponding distribution function, regarding the time-series samples values, induced by algorithm *distrIN* [2]. Figure 1c displays the membership-function-representation of IN F ; note that the latter matches the distribution function in Figure 1b. Finally, Figure 1d shows the equivalent, interval-representation of IN F using $L = 32$ intervals, where the reason for using $L = 32$ is explained in [30]. In conclusion, using only $L = 32$ numbers that define $L = 32$ intervals, we can potentially represent a distribution of samples. In the aforementioned sense, an IN with fairly few (i.e., $L = 32$) numbers can represent the distribution of orders of magnitude more numbers.

In all previous works, a whole time-series signal has been represented by a single IN, e.g., [2,5]. However, the latter representation suppresses the “time dimension” which constitutes a significant information content. To recover the “time dimension,” two alternatives have been examined here, namely Alternative 1 (AL1) and Alternative 2 (AL2), respectively, as explained in the following.

First, Alternative AL1 computes the cumulative sum (over time) of the samples' magnitude, normalized to $[0, 1]$. Figure 2 displays two INs induced from two EEG signals in two different classes, respectively, by Alternative AL1. Although time has been taken into account, there is no significant difference between the two INs in Figure 2 because the large number of involved samples resulted in very similar IN shapes. Hence, the distance between the two INs (computed by Equation (3)) is

negligible. The latter explains the poor classification results recorded in experiments we have carried out using AL1. Therefore, Alternative AL1 was abandoned.

Figure 1. Induction of IN F from an electroencephalography (EEG) signal: (a) An EEG signal. (b) The corresponding distribution function. (c) The membership-function-representation of the induced IN F matches its distribution function. (d) The interval-representation of IN F is shown for $L = 32$ intervals.

Figure 2. Plots of two different INs induced from two different EEG signals, respectively, both with 47,001 samples. The x -axis displays the number of samples, whereas the y -axis displays the normalized cumulative sum of the corresponding EEG amplitude samples. The intervals of the two INs are shown slightly displayed along the y -axis for comparison reasons.

Second, Alternative AL2 recovers (partly) the time dimension by partitioning the original time-series signal into consecutive windows; then, computing one IN per window. More specifically,

the time-series signal is partitioned in a number N of windows of equal length; then, from all the data in a window, one IN is induced per window by algorithm *distrIN* [2]. For instance, from the EEG signal in Figure 1a, using $N = 10$ windows, the ten INs of Figure 3 were induced. Such a (partial) recovery of time has improved classification performance as demonstrated below.

Figure 3. IN interval representations in $N = 10$ windows of the EEG signal shown in Figure 1a.

3.2. The Datasets

Two different datasets have been engaged regarding, first, electroencephalography (EEG) data and, second, audio data, as explained in the following.

3.2.1. Electroencephalography (EEG) Dataset

We considered the SEED dataset [41,42], which contains EEG data signals collected from 15 subjects (7 males and 8 females aged between 22 and 24 years old) while watching movie clips designed to elicit three types of emotions, namely “positive”, “neutral,” and “negative.” More specifically, each subject watched five clips for each types of emotion. The experiment was repeated three times. Therefore, the dataset included $3 \times 5 \times 15 = 225$ trials per emotion. Note that the recording device was an EEG cap conforming to the international 10–20 system (for 62 channels); hence, for each trial (i.e., for each movie clip) there were 62 signals corresponding to the 62 channels, respectively. An EEG signal was sampled at 200 Hz resulting in time-series with 37,001 to 47,001 samples per time-series. Our objective was to recognize the emotional state, namely “positive,” “neutral,” or “negative,” of individuals using EEG signals.

Of the 62 channels recorded by the EEG cap’s electrodes, not all were used in our emotion recognition computational experiments. Efficient emotion recognition calls for prior channel selection in order to reduce computational complexity. More specifically, channel selection depends on the brain region involved in processing, given the stimulus. Previous studies have identified appropriate channel groups [42,43]. For comparison purposes, the five groups of channels proposed in [44], including four channels per group, were used in this work. More specifically, Table 1 shows the channel groups used in our classification experiments. In addition to the aforementioned five channel groups, the set-union of the channels in the five groups was also considered resulting in nine channels, namely FP1, FT8, T7,T8, TP7, PO7, FC2, FPZ, F8. We point out that each signal was decomposed into delta (δ), theta (θ), alpha (α), beta (β), and gamma (γ) frequency bands [45].

Table 1. Groups of channels used in the classification experiments.

Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5
FP1, FT8, T7, T8	FT8, T7, T8, TP7	FT8, T7, T8, PO7	FP1, FC2, T8, TP7	FP1, FPZ, F8, T7

3.2.2. Audio Dataset

The objective here is spoken word classification using the Spoken Digits dataset [46], which contains 2000 recordings of English utterances of the ten digits “zero” to “nine” by four native English speakers. This dataset includes 200 signals per digit. Moreover, note that an audio signal was sampled at 8 KHz resulting in time-series with 1148 to 18,262 samples per time-series. Minimal silence was ensured by trimming the audio signal both at the beginning and at the end.

3.3. The Windowed Intervals’ Number kNN (WINKNN) Classifier

We assume a dataset including n_{trn} and n_{tst} subjects for training and testing, respectively. In particular, the data regarding a single subject includes n_{ch} time-series (i.e., channels). A time-series is optimally partitioned, as described below, in N parts, or equivalently windows, of equal length.

Algorithm 1 describes the windowed intervals’ number kNN (WINKNN) classifier for training. In particular, an optimal set of parameters is computed in Algorithm 1 using the GENETIC optimization detailed in the next section. Note that Algorithm 1 implements “leave-one-out” training per individual chromosome. Next, Algorithm 2 details testing by the WINKNN classifier.

Algorithm 1 Windowed Intervals’ Number kNN (WINKNN) classifier for training

0. Let k be the (integer) parameter of the kNN classifier; let n_{cl} be the total number of classes; let n_{trn} be the number of subjects for training; let n_{ch} be the number of channels per subject; let N be the number of windows per channel; a time-series in a channel is represented by an element $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{F}_1^N$; let N_G be the number of generations of the GENETIC algorithm;
 1. $m = 1$;
 2. **while** $m < N_G$ **do**
 3. **for** $i = 1$ to n_{trn} **do** %this loop is executed per chromosome $r \in \{1, \dots, n_r\}$;
 4. Initialize (i.e., set to zero) the vector $\text{ClassCounter}(1, \dots, n_{\text{cl}}) \leftarrow (0, \dots, 0)$;
 5. **for** $l = 1$ to n_{ch} **do**
 6. Calculate the set: $k\text{Winners}(i, l) = \underset{j \in \{1, \dots, n_{\text{trn}}\}, j \neq i}{\text{argmin}} D(\mathbf{F}_{i,l}, \mathbf{F}_{j,l})$ that holds the indices of the k nearest neighbors to $\mathbf{F}_{i,l} \in \mathbb{F}_1^N$ for $j \neq i$;
 7. Using the class labels of the k winners in the set $k\text{Winners}(i, l)$, update (i.e., increase the corresponding entries of) vector $\text{ClassCounter}(1, \dots, n_{\text{cl}})$;
 8. **end for**
 9. The subject i is classified to the class: $\text{argmax} \text{ClassCounter}(1, \dots, n_{\text{cl}})$;
 10. Update the success rate (fitness) Q_r per chromosome $r \in \{1, \dots, n_r\}$;
 11. **end for**
 12. GENETIC optimization of the “ $2 \cdot 2 \cdot N \cdot n_{\text{ch}} + 1$ ” parameters $v_0, v_1, \theta_0, \theta_1$ per window per channel as well as parameter k of the WINKNN classifier;
 13. $m \leftarrow m + 1$;
 14. **end while**
-

Algorithm 2 Windowed Intervals' Number kNN (WINKNN) classifier for testing

0. Let k be the (integer) parameter of the kNN classifier; let n_{cl} be the total number of classes; let n_{ch} be the number of channels per subject; let N be the number of windows per channel; a time-series in a channel is represented by an element $F \in F_1^N$; consider a subject $F_0 \in F_1^N \ l \in \{1, \dots, n_{ch}\}$ for classification;
 1. Initialize (i.e., set to zero) the vector $ClassCounter(1, \dots, n_{cl}) \leftarrow (0, \dots, 0)$;
 2. **for** $l = 1$ to n_{ch} **do**
 3. Calculate the set: $kWinners(l) = \underset{j \in \{1, \dots, n_{tm}\}}{\text{argmin}} D(F_{0,l}, F_{j,l})$ that holds the indices of the k nearest neighbors to $F_0 \in F_1^N \ l \in \{1, \dots, n_{ch}\}$;
 4. Update (i.e., increase the corresponding entries of) vector $ClassCounter(1, \dots, n_{cl})$ by considering the class labels of the k winners in the set $kWinners(l)$;
 5. **end for**
 6. The subject F_0 is classified to the class: $\underset{j \in \{1, \dots, n_{cl}\}}{\text{argmax}} ClassCounter(j)$.
-

3.4. GENETIC Optimization

As mentioned above, the distance between two INs is calculated based on the two parametric functions $v(x)$ and $\theta(x)$ per window per channel. The parameter values of the aforementioned functions affect the metric distance, and as a result, the classification performance changes. To determine an optimal set of parameters that maximizes classification performance, a GENETIC algorithm was employed as detailed next.

During an initialization step, a population of n_r chromosomes was considered. Each chromosome represented the set of parameters for classification. More specifically, for linear $v(x)$ and $\theta(x)$ functions, there were two parameters per function (v_1/v_0 and θ_1/θ_0 , respectively) that define slope and position. To enhance flexibility in tuning, we considered different pairs of functions $v(x)$ and $\theta(x)$ per window per channel. For example, to classify EEG signals with 9 channels, where each signal was partitioned in $N = 5$ windows, we used $2 \cdot 2 \cdot 5 \cdot 9 = 180$ parameters. Moreover, an additional parameter was used for the k value of the kNN classifier. Figure 4 shows the structure of a chromosome for n_{ch} channels and N windows per (time-series) signal.

Channel_1				...	Channel_n _{ch}				
Window1	Window2	...	WindowN	...	Window1	Window2	...	WindowN	
$v_1v_0\theta_1\theta_0$	$v_1v_0\theta_1\theta_0$...	$v_1v_0\theta_1\theta_0$...	$v_1v_0\theta_1\theta_0$	$v_1v_0\theta_1\theta_0$...	$v_1v_0\theta_1\theta_0$	k

Figure 4. Structure of a chromosome containing the classification parameters.

An initial population of n_r chromosomes (i.e., individuals) was randomly generated under constraints, namely the parametric functions $v(x)$ and $\theta(x)$ must be monotonically increasing and decreasing, respectively. Then, the fitness (i.e., cost) function of the GENETIC algorithm was computed as follows. Given n_{cl} classes, the result of a classification cycle, regarding all the n_{tst} subjects for testing, is a $n_{cl} \times n_{cl}$ confusion matrix B including classification percentages. In conclusion, the following fitness function was used per chromosome:

$$Q_r = 100 - (B_{11} + B_{22} + \dots + B_{n_{cl}n_{cl}}) / n_{cl}, \text{ where } r \in \{1, \dots, n_r\} \tag{6}$$

The cost function Q_r indicates how well a set of parameters defines distances that improve classification. Initially, all individuals are evaluated and they are sorted according to cost. To speed up data processing, parallel processing was applied for the evaluation of the individuals. Next, the individual selection procedure was applied to replace the parental population using tournament selection followed by genetic crossover and mutation; in particular, crossover was applied with probability $cxpb = 0.7$, whereas mutation was applied with probability $mutpb = 0.02$.

4. Experiments and Results

Two different sets of experiments have been conducted to demonstrate the capacity of the proposed WINKNN classifier regarding, first, an emotion classification task using EEG signals and, second, a word classification task using auditory signals. In each experiment, a single subject was left out for testing; eventually, every subject was left out exactly once for testing. In the aforementioned manner we estimated the generalization capacity of the WINKNN classifier. For both datasets, during the GENETIC optimization, the parameter values $n_r = 200$ and $N_G = 50$ were selected empirically.

4.1. Electroencephalography (EEG) Signal Classification

An optimal number N of windows was estimated, in the first place. In particular, before any optimization, classification experiments were carried out for an increasing number of 2, 3, 4, 5, 10, 15, and 20 windows. Table 2 shows the corresponding classification results. It was observed that when signals were partitioned to more than 5 windows, there was no significant improvement in classification performance; moreover, the computational cost was increasing rapidly for more than 5 windows. In conclusion, we decided to use $N = 5$ windows.

Table 3 displays the results obtained by the WINKNN classifier comparatively with the results by alternative classification methods from the literature.

Table 2. Optimal empirical estimation of the number N of windows.

No. of Windows:	1	2	3	4	5	10	15	20
Classification with $v(x) = x$ and $\theta(x) = -x$	48.9%	56.4%	57.0%	58.7%	61.6%	63.1%	61.5%	63.4%

Table 3. Results of the WINKNN classifier on the SEED dataset comparatively with alternative methods from the literature.

Method	No. of Channels	δ	θ	Frequency Bands			$\alpha + \beta + \gamma + \delta + \theta$
				α	β	γ	
GSCCA [44]	4	49.68	57.80	59.57	60.32	63.56	80.20
GSCCA [44]	12	56.31	65.88	69.98	78.06	78.48	83.72
GSCCA [44]	20	57.70	66.31	73.94	80.07	78.22	82.45
GSCCA [47]	62	52.36	60.59	65.52	71.63	72.19	74.84
CCA [48]	62	52.14	60.43	65.20	71.28	71.80	74.76
SVM [49]	62	56.04	63.23	67.07	74.95	75.97	85.23
SVM [42]	62	60.50	60.95	66.64	80.76	79.56	83.99
DNN [42]	62	64.32	60.77	64.01	78.92	79.19	86.08
INKNN with $\sigma_n(k)$	4	72.60 (k = 7)	74.50 (k = 6)	74.60 (k = 6)	73.80 (k = 9)	76.00 (k = 6)	80.59 (k = 10)
INKNN with distance (k)	4	67.11 (k = 6)	69.93 (k = 5)	67.41 (k = 6)	66.37 (k = 5)	68.59 (k = 7)	74.67 (k = 8)
WINKNN with distance (k)	4	76.00 (k = 4)	77.33 (k = 5)	79.55 (k = 5)	77.19 (k = 5)	77.33 (k = 7)	82.67 (k = 6)

It can be seen that the classification performance of our proposed WINKNN classifier is comparable to more complex (therefore more computationally expensive) classification techniques that make use of the entire set of available cap electrodes and, in some cases, it is superior, especially when a small number of channels is used. Even though alternative approaches are based on feature extraction, our method operates on raw data—in other words, no ad hoc feature extraction has been carried out whatsoever. The windowed IN approach is also superior to the authors’ previous work where a single IN was used to represent the entire signal [5]. It was also observed during the experiments that WINKNN was robust in terms of the consistency of classification results. Despite the fact that EEG signals stemming even from the same subject in response to same stimuli are not repeatable, the aforementioned consistency of the WINKNN classifier was remarkable and attributed to the representation of a data distribution by an IN.

During GENETIC optimization, the parameter ranges $v_1 \in [0,10]$, $v_0 \in [-1500,1500]$, $\theta_1 \in [0,10]$, $\theta_0 \in [-1500,1500]$, $k \in [4,10]$ were used; moreover, n_{ch} was either $n_{ch} = 4$ or $n_{ch} = 9$. Figure 5 shows an example of the improvement in classification performance resulting from the application of the GENETIC algorithm. Furthermore, Table 4 displays a set of optimal parameter values computed by GENETIC optimization for channel group G1, for all windows in all channels.

Figure 5. Classification performance improvement using GENETIC optimization.

Table 4. Typical, optimal parameters computed for the channel group G1 for $k = 5$.

		Window 1	Window 2	Window 3	Window 4	Window 5
Channel 1	v_1	9.792	7.809	1.993	2.240	7.277
	v_0	-1461.384	61.865	-1038.853	-464.432	-1111.372
	θ_1	6.728	3.710	3.190	8.952	7.908
	θ_0	-465.901	-331.331	1414.876	-462.023	760.318
Channel 2	v_1	5.955	0.010	0.895	3.953	2.289
	v_0	-601.800	1296.741	1321.715	-654.458	-1313.372
	θ_1	6.548	5.942	0.063	2.614	9.439
	θ_0	-1138.014	-844.781	333.440	1180.064	1419.705
Channel 3	v_1	6.837	10	10	5.107	0.639
	v_0	-1292.576	22.847	1035.796	816.906	353.922
	θ_1	8.260	9.918	10	7.265	2.313
	θ_0	-1075.657	88.849	-839.725	-159.621	-1079.277
Channel 4	v_1	6.802	2.444	0.061	8.133	1.581
	v_0	-987.327	1093.856	-377.266	-187.907	1181.140
	θ_1	1.065	-0.006	7.706	7.656	1.597
	θ_0	-936.397	1448.139	115.220	-179.689	-941.193

4.2. Audio Signal Classification

An optimal number $N = 15$ of windows was estimated by trial-and-error as in the previous section regarding EEGs; furthermore, one IN was induced per window. Three different experiments were carried out including: (a) 3 classes (spoken digits “0”, “5” and “9”), (b) 5 classes (spoken digits “0”, “3”, “5”, “7” and “9”), and (c) 10 classes for all ten spoken digits.

During GENETIC optimization, the parameter ranges $v_1 \in [0,10]$, $v_0 \in [-1000,1000]$, $\theta_1 \in [0,10]$, $\theta_0 \in [-1000,1000]$, $k \in [4,10]$ were used; moreover, $n_{ch} = 1$. Table 5 shows the classification results by the WINKNN classifier compared to the authors’ previous results [50] (in brackets), where a time-series was represented by a single IN. For all aforementioned three class groups, the WINKNN classifier resulted in a superior improvement.

Table 5. Results by the WINKNN classifier compared to results by the “1 IN kNN classifier” (within parentheses) on the Spoken Digits dataset. The corresponding optimal “k” value is also shown.

	3 Classes	5 Classes	10 Classes
Default parameters (k = 4)	88.3% (70.5%)	81.9% (51.3%)	69.4% (34.45%)
Optimized parameters	92.5%, k = 6 (81%, k = 4)	86.4%, k = 6 (70.7%, k = 4)	75.7%, k = 8 (54%, k = 8)

4.3. Discussion

The use of a single IN to represent a time-series ignores the “time dimension” of a time-series signal; more specifically, it considers solely the distribution of the signal samples. Nevertheless, with the proposed WINKNN classifier, the “time dimension” is (partly) recovered toward improving classification performance. The classification results here have confirmed a consistent improvement in classification performance because of the partition of a time-series to more than 1 window.

It is observed that the improvement is larger for the experiments with the audio signals than with the EEG signals. This was explained by the fact that the information content in audio signals is more dependent on time, as opposed to the EEG signals which are significantly affected by a number of concurrent brain activations. Note also that not only EEG signals are subject-specific, but also the data in the trials, even per subject, are not repeatable, resulting in a decrease of classification performance for the EEG signals in comparison to audio signals.

Partitioning the signals to N time windows multiplies the total number of parameters of the WINKNN classifier. The latter increases the search space for the GENETIC algorithm and makes convergence to an optimal set of parameters slower. However, significant benefits are retained with N time windows including: (a) Substantial data reduction, compared to the raw data, because of the employment of “N” INs per channel; hence, the proposed techniques emerge promising for big data applications. (b) Time consuming, ad hoc feature extraction is not necessary; instead, all-order statistics are used implicitly as features for tunable classification using the optimizable, parametric WINKNN classifier. (c) Fairly heavy computational overhead is required only once, during training.

We remark that recently published classification techniques from the literature have reported higher classification results than the WINKNN classifier on the SEED (EEG) dataset but at the expense of considerably more time for computation, using all 64 channels as well as all frequency bands; moreover, ad hoc features had to be defined [14].

5. Conclusions

The interest of this work was in time-series classification regarding human-robot interaction. Our proposed novelty was to represent “time” by an N-tuple of INs instead of by a single IN. A novel windowed IN-based kNN, namely WINKNN, classifier was introduced and applied to two different benchmark classification datasets, namely the SEED dataset and the Spoken Digit dataset regarding the recognition of emotional states based on EEG signals and the recognition of spoken digits based on audio signals, respectively. Extensive computational experiments have demonstrated, comparatively, a superior performance of the WINKNN classifier.

The proposed WINKNN classifier used raw (time-series) data; in other words, no ad hoc feature extraction was necessary. The latter is considered to be a major advantage toward transferring IN-based techniques to a wide range of applications. Moreover, the performance of the proposed method can be optimized, parametrically. The capability of the WINKNN classifier was attributed (a) to the capacity of an IN to represent statistics of all-orders; the latter are the “features” engaged implicitly, (b) to the capacity to optimize, parametrically, the distance function, and (c) to the consideration of time.

Because of its capacity for representing a distribution of samples, an IN can potentially represent big data. Hence, IN-based techniques emerge promising in big data applications. Potential future

work may include various time-series applications to different domains such as medicine, physics, economics, agriculture, and elsewhere. The implicit employment of “all-order statistics” should also be studied. Further future work will pursue an engagement of INs with alternative architectures such as neural networks etc.

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